

Terpenoids: Part CII. A New Synthesis of 2-Methyl-5-isopropenylanisole

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2-Methyl-5-chlorophenol, prepared from 2-methyl-5-chloroaniline, on methylation with dimethylsulphate and potassium hydroxide, gives 2-methyl-5-chloroanisole (IV). The compound (IV) on reaction with lithium diisopropenyl copper reagent furnishes 2-methyl-5-isopropenylanisole.

THOMAS and coworkers isolated a new substance having a strong smell of the kind of thymol from *Hinoki oil*^{1,2} and identified it as 2-methyl-5-isopropenylanisole (I). The structure (I) was based on the IR, NMR data and also upon its chemical reactions. This has further been confirmed through a synthesis³.

The present communication reports another unambiguous synthesis of the title compound using the reaction of lithium-diisopropenyl copper reagent for the introduction of an isopropenyl group in the molecule. The sequence of the reactions is given below :

2-methyl-5-chloroaniline (II) was diazotised with HCl/NaNO₂ at 0°-5° and the resulting diazonium compound was steam distilled to get 2-methyl-5-chlorophenol (III). Methylation of the substituted phenol (III) with dimethylsulphate in the presence of aq. potassium hydroxide afforded the methyl ether (IV) in 80% yield. The chloroanisole (IV) on reaction with lithium diisopropenyl copper⁴ at 0° and in an atmosphere of nitrogen, furnished the title compound (I) in 72% yield. The purity of the synthesised compound was checked by tlc (single spot). Its IR spectrum was identical with that of authentic sample.

Experimental

The b.pts. are uncorrected. IR spectra were obtained on Perkin Elmer 337 Infrared spectrophotometer as thin liquid film, using sodium chloride optics.

2-Methyl-5-chlorophenol (III) :

2-Methyl-5-chloroaniline (II, 15 g) was dissolved in 5*N* HCl (138 ml) and the resulting solution was stirred for 10 min. at 40°. To the cooled solution at 0°-5° was added a saturated cold solution of sodium nitrate (8.5 g) slowly and with constant shaking to an end point with potassium iodide-starch paper. After leaving the mixture at room temp. for 15 min, the excess acid was destroyed by adding crystalline urea carefully. The clear solution was added dropwise to 20% sulphuric acid (100 ml) and the reaction mixture was steam distilled. The distillate was saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with ether. The combined extracts were washed with brine and dried. The solvent was evaporated and the residual oil distilled under reduced pressure to give phenolic compound (III), b.p. 160°-65°/2-3 mm. yield 9 g (60%). γ_{max} 3340, 1500, 1350, 1250, 815, 780 and 740 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 58.48; H, 5.00. C₇H₇OCl requires C, 58.96; H, 4.91%).

2-Methyl-5-chloroanisole (IV) :

To a solution of sodium hydroxide (14 g) in water (140 ml) was added the compound (III, 47.5 g). The resulting solution was cooled to about 10° and dimethylsulphate (42 g) was added dropwise during 1 hr with constant shaking. Thereafter the contents were heated under reflux for 2 hr., cooled to room temp. and extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed successively with dil. sulphuric acid and water. After removing the solvent, the residue was distilled to afford (IV, 40 g), yield 80%, b.p.

89°-90°/5 mm. γ_{max} 1600, 1500, 825 and 715 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 61.53; H, 54.49. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{OCl}$ requires C, 61.34; H, 5.75%).

2-Methyl-5-isopropenylanisole (I) :

Lithium diisopropenyl copper reagent was prepared from isopropenyl lithium (32 ml, 6.4 N) and copper iodide (9.6 g) in ether at -10° . The resulting product was stirred at the same temp. for 30 min. followed by the dropwise addition of the chloride (IV, 1.5 g) in THF (15 ml). After leaving at this temperature for 20 hr the reaction mixture was decomposed with ice-cold water and the product was extracted with ether. The combined extract was washed with water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent and distillation under reduced pressure followed by chromatography over neutral alumina using pet-ether as eluent gave (I, 1.3 g) in 80% yield, b.p. 97°-99°/8 mm.

γ_{max} 3060, 1640, 1605, 1570, 1240, 1195, 1175, 1128, 1095, 988, 872, 835, 800, 755 and 710 cm^{-1} . $\lambda_{max}^{ethanol} = 210, 249$ and $292 \text{ m}\mu$. This data is identical with those reported in lit.³. (Found : C, 81.27; H, 8.86. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires C, 81.44; H, 8.70%).

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